

Effect of mulching on wheat yield under line and broadcast seeding, Daudkandi, Bangladesh, 1982-83.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)	Return ^a (\$/ha)	Total variable cost ^b (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)
Line seeding, mulch	3.0	381	147	234
Line seeding, no mulch	2.5	317	145	172
Broadcast, mulch	2.9	368	144	224
Broadcast, no mulch	2.3	292	143	149

^a Wheat price = \$127/t. ^b Price of straw-mulch (\$17/ha) was also included in the economic analysis. Design: randomized complete block, 3 replications; variety Sonalika. Fertilizer rate = 80-26-33 kg N-P-K/ha. Seed rate = 120 kg/ha.

soil moisture, protected seeds from birds, and reduced weed growth. Planting method had little effect on yield. □

Individuals, organizations, and media are invited to quote or reprint articles or excerpts from articles in the IRRN.

Announcements

Azolla newsletter

IRRI will begin publishing in August 1985 a semi-annual *Azolla Newsletter* for workers interested in azolla, blue-green algae, and biological N fixation. The newsletter will help workers to share information, to keep abreast of developments in the field, and to maintain current information on azolla specimen collections throughout the world.

The newsletter will include 1) abstracts of azolla publications, 2) current issues in azolla research and use, 3) reports and recommendations of azolla meetings, 4) news of live and herbaria specimen collections, and 5) specimen accession announcements.

The *Azolla Newsletter* was recommended at the International Workshop on Azolla Use at Fuzhou, China, 31 Mar to 5 Apr 1985. For a free subscription to the newsletter, write: Dr. Iwao Watanabe, Soil Microbiology Department, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

Contributions to the *Azolla Newsletter* should be sent to any of the five regional editors. They are Liu Chung-chu (Asia), Vice President, Soil and Fertilizer Institute, Fujian Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Fuzhou, Fujian, China;

T. A. Lumpkin (North and South America), Department of Agronomy, Washington State University, Pullman, WA 99164-6420, USA

Elizabeth G. Cutter (Europe), Department of Botany, University of Manchester, Manchester M13 9PL, United Kingdom;

B. W. Norton (Australia), Department of Agriculture, University of Queensland, St. Lucia, Queensland, Australia 4067; or

H. F. Diara (Africa), West Africa Rice Development Association, B.P. 96, Saint Louis, Senegal.

Rice straw as cattle feed

The National Livestock Development Board, Mahaweli Authority of Sri Lanka Draft Animal Program, Animal Science Department of the University of Peradeniya, and the Sri Lanka-Netherlands Livestock Development Program are planning an international seminar for extension workers and research fellows working with rice straw as cattle feed. For further information regarding the seminar, tentatively scheduled for mid-1985, write the Coordinator, Straw Utilization Project, P. O. Box 138, Kandy, Sri Lanka. □

Watanabe receives Japanese soil science award

I. Watanabe, head of the IRRI Soil Microbiology Department, received the 30th award of the Japanese Soil Science Society on 7 Apr 1985 for his research on N fixation in tropical rice fields.

Watanabe graduated from the University of Tokyo in 1955 and received his D Agr in 1961. He has published more than 150 papers on N fixation and transformation and mineral nutrition. □

Conservation of crop germplasm — an international perspective

Conservation of crop germplasm — an international perspective, edited by W. L. Brown, T. T. Chang, M. M. Goodman, and Q. Jones, is a collection of six papers presented at a symposium on crop germplasm sponsored by the Crop Science Society of America. Subject matter ranges from a detailed description of the essential elements of successful plant exploration to the broadly defined goals and operations of national and international germplasm programs. The gene resource programs of two international agricultural research centers and germplasm conservation as practiced at the National Seed Storage Laboratory, Fort Collins, Colorado, also are described.

Price is US\$11 plus \$0.75 for all orders from outside the United States. Payment must accompany the order. For further information, write: CSSA Headquarters Office, Attn. Book Order Department, 677 S. Segoe Road, Madison, WI 53711, USA. □

New IRRI publications

New publications are available for purchase at the Communication and Publications Department, Division R, IRRI, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines:

IRRI highlights 1984

Illustrated guide to integrated pest management in rice in tropical Asia, by W. H. Reissig, E. A. Heinrichs, J. A.